

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP2 - Pilots implementation and open call Documenting collaborations with video annotation: MemoRekall Capsules

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MemoRekall Capsule

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I. MemoRekall

MemoRekall (www.memorekall.com) is a free and open-source web app to explain and annotate a video enhanced by adding notes, documents, or web links. Their organization is developed from and around the video recording in hypertextual logic. MemoRekall proposes a multi-document, temporal and spatial reading of a work from its video recording. The result is called a « capsule ». As the consultation progresses, the reader discovers annotations and other documents, which they can open and consult as they please, and then return to the video recording. MemoRekall is at the crossroads of enhancing existing digital cultural documents, creating enriched cultural content, and setting up critical and collaborative spaces. Using the same video, different documentary strategies can be developed, depending on the issues specific to each capsule author: artists need to document their works so that they can be easily disseminated, adapted, or recreated; cultural institutions wish to share the creative process with their audiences, as well as elements of analysis on their websites; teachers need to present their students with different multimedia resources to accompany their courses on the history of the performing arts or as part of pedagogical activities related to performances seen in the classroom¹.

II. Documenting a collaboration

During the COESO project Pilot 2, “Dancing Philosophy”, MemoRekall was used to document the creative process, the collaboration between the choreographer and the philosopher, and the workshops with the students. The main perspective is a close reading and qualitative approach to collaboration documentation. Six capsules will be created. All the capsules will be available on the Pilot 2 blog, <https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/>.

We present here briefly the first one:

<https://project.memorekall.com//dancing-philosophy---une-personne-prendre-d%C3%A9poser-sasseoir-se-lever//?w=1>

The capsule “*Prendre déposer s’asseoir se lever*” was realized during a two-day workshop at Université Polytechnique Hauts-de-France with students from the MA “*Création numérique – parcours Scénarisation et Réalisation Transmédia*” and Pilot 2 team. The challenge of the workshop was to propose a journey in which the participants were actively involved and which intertwined dance, philosophy, notation, staging, and video recording. The aim was to provoke reflection on the links between the search for words, the experience of movement, and the production of images to feed the students' training path in connection with the reflections and creative process developed in Pilot 2. The capsule focuses on the protocol developed by Irénée Blin and Daniele Marranca, following the first requests of Cosetta Graffione to Stefania Ferrando (all COESO Pilot 2 members) in terms of movement: to go down, to lie down on the floor, and to go up, looking for the most logical coordination possible in relation to a functional body organization. The students were introduced to Laban kinetography and were asked to draw their path in space. In addition, Irénée Blin analyzed the movement of each participant and proposed

¹ For more details on MemoRekall, see Bardiot, Clarisse. 2021. *Performing Arts and Digital Humanities: From Traces to Data*. Hoboken: ISTE / Wiley.

different ways to note this "simple" movement with Laban notation: sitting on the floor and standing up. Thanks to a split-screen, the end of the video recording shows a comparison between all the participants. Sébastien Hildebrand produced the editing in close collaboration with Pilot 2 team members.

III. Designing new functionalities

The working process of making the capsule was also the occasion between Clarisse Bardiot, Irénée Blin, and the other Pilot 2 team members to design new MemoRekall functionalities. The main research question is: is MemoRekall suitable for documenting a collaboration between a researcher and an artist? MemoRekall was used to document collaborations between artists and scientists for another European project. Annick Bureaud, who was in charge of this documentation, realized a capsule for each work following an editorial protocol (see <https://www.olats.org/feat/>) that we would like to expand. Documenting the collaboration between a dancer and a philosopher during COESO Pilot 2 led to new questions: how to expand MemoRekall's capacity to link documents? How to explain the Laban notation scores to a general audience? Is the video recording the main document? These questions drive the development of MemoRekall's new functionalities, which will be implemented in the following months within the COESO project.